

LUND
UNIVERSITY

2026-03-26

STYR 2024/3316

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

Vice-Chancellor

Lund University's Action Plan for Research Assessment Reform 2025-2029

Lund University joined the *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)* on 29 November 2022. This action plan outlines Lund University's core priorities and actions to align assessment of research and researchers with the *Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)*. It furthermore links to relevant international frameworks adopted by the university.

Lund University has a long-standing commitment to responsible research assessment, with many ARRA requirements already embedded in existing practices or advanced through recent initiatives. This action plan is, however, a dynamic, future-oriented document focusing on current and planned initiatives to implement CoARA Commitments and Principles, rather than providing an exhaustive account of established procedures and practices that support CoARA's vision.

Lund University has joined CoARA viewing it as a strategic tool to help maximise the quality and impact of research. Efforts to transform the culture of research assessment bring several advantages: they broaden evaluation criteria to recognise a wider diversity of research contributions—benefiting cross- and interdisciplinary work—foster innovation by encouraging risk-taking and promote equal opportunities by minimising bias. Altogether, CoARA strengthens the university's ability to compete on a global scale.

The aim of this document is to support a transparent, fair and responsible assessment culture that aligns with international standards and best practices. It also establishes clear responsibilities for the CoARA implementation at Lund University, alongside responsibilities for proactive monitoring of developments to support evidence-based improvements of assessment practices. In line with CoARA instructions, the action plan will be reviewed and updated after five years, with internal follow-ups on a regular basis.

A preparatory CoARA project is ongoing from January 2025 to December 2026, with the aim of organising the work and allocating roles and responsibilities both within support and core activities. During 2025 a mapping exercise has been carried out to identify the CoARA-relevant current and planned activities. The action plan has been prepared by a project group led by the Pro Vice-Chancellor for Integrity and Character, with support from the divisions Human Resources and Research, Collaboration and Innovation. As part of the preparations, all faculties were consulted to gather input and secure engagement from the university's core activities.

Lund University identifies six core priorities to further reform research assessment, each supported by concrete actions:

1. Safeguard and strengthen **academic freedom**, scientific **integrity**, and **inclusiveness**
2. Uphold the **HR Excellence in Research** award by fulfilling the requirements for a responsible and professional employer, according to the principles in the European Charter for Researchers
3. Promote **peer review** as the foundation for research quality assessment
4. Develop responsible and transparent **benchmarking** practices
5. Enable and encourage **open science** practices
6. **Communicate** progress and exchange practices for **mutual learning**

Lund University's core priorities and actions

1. Safeguard and strengthen academic freedom, scientific integrity and inclusiveness

All researchers have the right to freely define research questions, select appropriate methods, and publish their findings. Lund University recognises that responsible assessment frameworks support these rights, as well as uphold scientific integrity and equal opportunities as non-negotiable principles. Towards these ends, Lund University have signed *Magna Charta Universitatum*¹.

Selection of established internal practices and initiatives linked to the priority:

- Lund University Council for Ethics and Academic Freedom²
- Gender equality and equal opportunities at Lund University³

Actions

- Finalise and adopt the Lund University Declaration on Academic Freedom
- Utilise the insights from the initiative to educate “Critical friends” to address unconscious bias in research assessment

2. Uphold the HR Excellence in Research award by fulfilling the requirements for a responsible and professional employer, according to the principles in the European Charter for Researchers

Lund University is committed to being an attractive, fair and responsible employer for researchers at all career stages. The HR Excellence in Research Award is a recognised mark of quality and aligns with CoARA in its vision for a sustainable, fair, and responsible research system. Synergies are evident in

¹ <https://www.magna-charta.org/magna-charta-universitatum>

² <https://etikradet.blogg.lu.se/>

³ <https://www.staff.lu.se/organisation-and-governance/vision-objectives-and-strategies/gender-equality-and-equal-opportunities>

their shared objective to broaden the criteria by which research and researchers are valued, as well as in efforts to enhance recruitment practices and adapt support structures in response to assessment reform. Lund University has within this context adopted the *European Charter for Researchers*⁴.

Information on both previous and current initiatives and practises relating to the implementation of the HR Excellence in research framework:

- Lund University external website on HR Excellence in research Award⁵
- Lund University Internal web page in Swedish on HR Excellence in research Award⁶

Actions

- Enhance the knowledge of strategic recruitment and talent management, in preparation for the joint university planning process
- Implement a forum for mutual learning and development of the recruitment process by Academic Appointment boards

3. Promote peer review as the foundation for research quality assessment

Peer review remains the most robust method for assessing quality as it is grounded in the expertise of the research community. Assessment of research or researchers should therefore primarily rely on peer-reviewed qualitative judgment, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators and metrics.

At Lund University, the enhancement of research must be characterised by peer-review mechanisms, such as external and internal expert review. Quality management of research is based on work that is systematic, documented and followed up. Peer review is the driving principle for high quality. At faculties, departments and in research environments, quality and relevance are assessed continuously in both internal and external processes, nationally and internationally. Metrics should be applied responsibly, guided by *The Metric Tide* report⁷.

Importantly, quantitative indicators and metrics are not inherently problematic in research assessment; the issue arises from using their results uncritically. To encourage responsible procedures and practices when using quantitative indicators and/or metrics in assessment of research and researchers, Lund University acknowledges KU Leuven's position on the use of metrics in the assessment of research(ers)⁸ and the *Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics*⁹.

Selection of established internal practices and initiatives linked to the priority:

⁴ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/hrexcellenceaward/european-charter-researchers>

⁵ <https://www.lunduniversity.lu.se/about-university/work-lund-university/hr-excellence-research-award>

⁶ <https://www.medarbetarwebben.lu.se/organisation-och-styrning/organisation/utvecklingsprojekt/hr-excellence-research-award-handlingsplan-2023-2025>

⁷ <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/RE-151221-TheMetricTideFullReportExecSummary.pdf>

⁸ <https://research.kuleuven.be/en/policy-figures/responsible-use-of-metrics>

⁹ <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org>

- Guidelines for Quality Assurance and Quality Enhancement of Research at Lund University¹⁰

Actions

- Continue developing a unified Research Quality Assurance System that prioritises peer review and evaluates procedures in line with CoARA Commitments and Principles.

4. Develop responsible benchmarking practices

Lund University aims to be a leading international university, with an increased international impact. In order to reach this, it is important to compare our performance with that of others and to capture messages on how we are perceived by students, colleagues and employers internationally. Lund University uses ranking results and benchmarking for this purpose. This use is among others informed by *Leiden Ranking Principles for Responsible Use*¹¹. In accordance, the University uses ranking results as one of several alternative sources for structured comparisons of research practices, performance and outcomes against international peers and standards. The goal is to identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvements on an institutional level. Lund University also recognises the methodological limitations of international rankings and avoids the use of metrics by international rankings to assess individual researchers or research units.

Selection of established internal practices and initiatives linked to the priority:

- Lund University's work with benchmarking is led at Pro Vice-Chancellor level. A strategic analysis unit supports the university management with defining metrics, which includes quality assessment and ranking activities.

Actions

- Clarify principles for and communicate purpose of ranking activities.

5. Enable and encourage open science practices

Lund University strives to ensure that research and its dissemination is characterised by openness, efficiency, and accessibility. The University adheres to *UNESCO's Recommendations on Open Science*¹² and seeks to establish open science practices as self-evident criteria within assessment frameworks for research and researchers.

Selection of established internal practices and initiatives linked to the priority:

- Research Strategy Lund University 2023-2026¹³
- Platform for Strategic Work Lund University 2025-2027¹⁴

¹⁰ <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2025-04/guidelines-for-quality-assurance-and-quality-enhancement-of-research-at-lund-university.pdf>

¹¹ <https://www.leidenranking.com>

¹² <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

¹³ <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2023-09/Forskningsstrategi%20ENG%20tillg%C3%A4nglig%20230315.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2025-03/Platform%20for%20Strategic%20Work%202025-2027.pdf>

- Open access policy for publications and artistic works¹⁵
- Lund University Research Data Office, which has a coordinating role and works to strengthen the quality and impact of research, by supporting researchers to make data more accessible, secure and sustainable, in accordance with legal requirements and principles for open science.
- Working group for Open Science. Appointed by the university research board this group is tasked with monitoring and analysing matters related to open science.¹⁶
- University wide support for Lund University researchers to publish open access, including funding through national publishing agreements and local APC-funds.¹⁷

Actions

- Annual follow up on open science at Lund University in relation to the roadmap for open science¹⁸ established by The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions and the National Guidelines for Open Science¹⁹.
- Evaluate and revise university strategies and policies, and guidelines that address any aspect of open science.
- Centrally support yearly initiatives and events where researchers and support staff can learn and exchange experiences of engaging in open science.

6. Communicate progress and exchange practises for mutual learning

Demonstrating progress in implementing and adhering to the ARRA is a key aspect of the CoARA initiative. It fosters both mutual learning and requires careful self-reflection by monitoring one's own compliance and progress. By participating in and communicating through internal and external forums, Lund University seeks to remain aligned with international best practices, uphold accountability to this action plan, and promote responsible research assessment within the University, as well as globally.

Lund University is conducting a feasibility study to map out how research content can be more comprehensively and accessibly presented on the web. One important communication channel is the Lund University Research Portal, which plays a key role in fostering a more transparent and qualitative approach to research assessment. By highlighting the breadth and depth of research outputs across the university, it showcases the true diversity of our research. When fully utilised, the portal's direct access to researcher profiles, publications, projects and collaborations supports an assessment culture that values institutional strengths.

¹⁵ <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2021-09/Open-access-policy-for-publications-and-artistic-works.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://www.staff.lu.se/research-and-education/research-support/research-board/working-group-open-science>

¹⁷ <https://www.ub.lu.se/en/publish/open-access>

¹⁸ <https://suhf.se/app/uploads/2025/05/REC-2021-1-Open-Science-Roadmap-REVISED-08-05-2025-1-2.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kb:publ-738>

Lund University actively participates in CoARA's Swedish National Chapter and has appointed representatives to participate in two national working groups:

- WG2: Assessment of individual academics
- WG5: Merit evaluation in collaboration and societal impact

Lund University is also a member of European networks, such as LERU and CESAER, which are useful channels for mutual learning on CoARA-related aspects.

Within Lund University, the information channels of the divisions Human Resources and Research, Collaboration and Innovation will be used to disseminate information on CoARA to researchers and employees.

Actions

- Develop and launch a dedicated LU webpage about the process of implementing CoARA and link it to other relevant initiatives or support guides.
- Actively participate in national and international working groups and networks and establish channels to internalise good practice to research assessment.

Actions 2025-2029

2025

Focus

- Establishment of steering group and project group and development of action plan.
- Communicate the preparatory project externally and internally and secure buy-in from faculties and central administration.
- Engage with the Swedish national chapter, its working groups and the CoARA general assembly to exchange good practice and monitor global progress.

2026

Focus

- Propose internal governance and distribution of work on CoARA-related aspects.
- Submit Lund University's action plan to CoARA.
- Engage with the Swedish national chapter, its working groups and the CoARA general assembly to exchange good practice and monitor global progress.
- Annual follow up on open science and central support for learning and exchange of experiences on open science at Lund University.

Action	Responsibility	LU priority	CoARA principle(s)
Finalise and adopt the LU Declaration on Academic Freedom	Responsible project group	1	1
Utilise the insights from the initiative to educate "Critical friends" to address unconscious bias in research assessment	Project leader HUMLA project group (<i>Hållbar Utbildning för Medvetandegörande av Lika villkor i Akademin – 'Sustainable Education for raising awareness of equal opportunities in academia'</i>)	1	1, 6

Creation of forum for mutual learning and development of the recruitment process by Academic Appointment boards	Project leader for the implementation of HR for Excellence in Research at Lund University	2	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7
Continue developing a unified Research Quality Assurance System that prioritises peer review and evaluates procedures in line with CoARA Commitments and Principles.	Lund University-wide Research Board with support from Research Services	3	2, 6
Clarify principles for and communicate purpose of ranking activities.	Office of the Vice Chancellor with support from the Research and External Communication unit	4	4, 6
Develop and launch a dedicated LU webpage about the process of implementing CoARA and link it to other relevant initiatives or support guides.	CoARA project group	6	7, 9

2027

Focus

- Submitting final internal report on implementation project in early 2027.
- Engage with the Swedish national chapter, its working groups and the CoARA general assembly to exchange good practice and monitor global progress.
- Annual follow up on open science and central support for learning and exchange of experiences on open science at Lund University.

Action	Responsibility	LU priority	CoARA principle(s)
Assess the impact of the initiative to educate “Critical friends” to address unconscious bias in research assessment	Project leader HUMLA project group (<i>Hållbar Utbildning för Medvetandegörande av Lika villkor i Akademin – ‘Sustainable Education for raising awareness of equal opportunities in academia’</i>)	1	1, 6

Enhance the knowledge of strategic recruitment and talent management, in preparation for the joint university planning process	Project leader for the implementation of HR for Excellence in Research at Lund University	2	1,5, 7
Continue developing a unified Research Quality Assurance System that prioritises peer review and evaluates procedures in line with CoARA Commitments and Principles.	Lund University-wide Research Board with support from Research Services	3	2, 6
Evaluate and revise university strategies and policies, and guidelines that address any aspect of open science.	Lund University-wide Research Board with support from the University Library	5	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10

2028

Focus

- Follow up on progress regarding implementation.
- Engage with the Swedish national chapter, its working groups and the CoARA general assembly to exchange good practice and monitor global progress.
- Annual follow up on open science and central support for learning and exchange of experiences on open science at Lund University.

Action	Responsibility	LU priority	CoARA principle(s)
Finalise implementation of forum for mutual learning and development of the recruitment process by Academic Appointment boards	Project leader for the implementation of HR for Excellence in Research at Lund University	2	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7

2029

Focus

- Evaluate implemented actions.

- Engage with the Swedish national chapter, its working groups and the CoARA general assembly to exchange good practice and monitor global progress.
- Annual follow up on open science and central support for learning and exchange of experiences on open science at Lund University.

Annex

The Commitments

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research